

FRIES REACTION WITH ARYL *o*-TOLUENESULPHONATES AND ARYL ALKANESULPHONATE

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Phenyl *o*-toluenesulphonate undergoes the Fries reaction when heated with anhydrous aluminium chloride to afford a mixture of *o*- and *p*-hydroxysulphones. *p*-Tolyl and *p*-chlorophenyl *o*-toluenesulphonates isomerise to 2-hydroxy-5:2'-dimethyldiphenylsulphone and 5-chloro-2-hydroxy-2'-methyl-diphenylsulphone respectively. Aryl alkanesulphonates do not undergo the reaction.

The work reported in this communication is a continuation of what has been reported earlier (Aleykutty and Baliah, *Curr. Sci.*, 1953, 22, 307; this *Journal*, 1954, 31, 513; 1955, 32, 773; 1956, 33, 189). The Fries rearrangement of phenyl, *p*-tolyl and *p*-chlorophenyl *o*-toluenesulphonates has been studied in the present investigation. When phenyl *o*-toluenesulphonate was heated with anhydrous aluminium chloride at 130-40° for 45 minutes, it isomerised to the extent of 47%. At a lower temperature (120-25°) the isomerised product was only 31%. Both the *o*- and *p*-hydroxysulphones were present in the product. The difference in their solubilities in non-polar solvents like benzene and ligroin was not much and, hence, easy separation could not be effected. Repeated fractional crystallisation from ligroin gave 2-hydroxy-2'-methyl-diphenylsulphone alone in a pure condition. The *p*-isomer could not be purified. The two isomers were synthesised unequivocally and the identity of the Fries product, which was obtained pure, was established by comparison with the synthetic sample.

The Fries reaction of *p*-tolyl *o*-toluenesulphonate furnished a hydroxysulphone which was identical with 2-hydroxy-5:2'-dimethyldiphenylsulphone, synthesised as follows:

p-Chlorophenyl *o*-toluenesulphonate isomerised analogously, yielding 5-chloro-2-hydroxy-2'-methyl-diphenylsulphone. The identity of this sulphone also has been established by a similar unambiguous synthesis.

A striking observation made in the present investigation is the failure of aryl alkanesulphonates to undergo the isomerisation. This difference in the behaviour of

aryl arenesulphonates and aryl alkanesulphonates becomes significant when we bear in mind that no such difference exists in the case of aryl esters derived from aromatic and aliphatic carboxylic acids.

Attempts were made to isomerise *p*-tolyl methanesulphonate, *p*-tolyl ethanesulphonate and *p*-tolyl phenylmethanesulphonate. In no case the reaction occurred. For example, *p*-tolyl ethanesulphonate, when heated with aluminium chloride in nitrobenzene at 140-50° for 3 hours, gave only an intractable tar. Lowering of the temperature and reducing the time of heating did not prove helpful. It appeared worthwhile to try a milder catalyst. With zinc chloride, even at 160°, the sulphonate remained unchanged.

Generally, the esters of sulphonic acids isomerise less readily than the esters of carboxylic acids. Further, we find that the esters of aliphatic sulphonic acids undergo no isomerisation at all. This difference in the behaviour of sulphonates and carboxylic esters seems to arise from the difference in the stabilities of the cation intermediates in the reaction. The generally accepted mechanism of the Fries reaction postulates the formation of an acyl carbonium ion as an intermediate, and this ion makes an electrophilic attack on the aromatic nucleus. The acyl carbonium ions derived from aliphatic and aromatic carboxylic acids can have the following hyperconjugated or resonance structures :

They are thus stabilised and their formation is facilitated. Though resonance structures such as (II), (III) etc. are possible for the ions derived from sulphonates, their formation is less facile than that of acyl carbonium ions because resonance involves double bond formation between sulphur and carbon.

According to the overlap principle a *2p-2p* π -bond is more easily formed than a *3p-2p* π -bond. Hence, the acyl ions result more easily than the arene- or alkane-sulphonyl ions.

EXPERIMENTAL

The Fries Rearrangement of Phenyl o-Toluenesulphonate.—An intimate mixture of phenyl *o*-toluenesulphonate (37.2 g.) and finely powdered anhydrous aluminium

chloride (30 g.) was heated at 130-40° for 45 minutes. After cooling, the product was treated with HCl in crushed ice and extracted with ether. The ether solution was then extracted with a 10% solution of NaOH until most of the alkali-soluble product was removed from it. The combined alkali extract was acidified. The precipitated hydroxysulphone, which was in a semi-solid condition, hardened after drying in a vacuum desiccator. It weighed 17.3 g. (47%). The product, on extraction with hot ligroin and evaporation of the solvent, gave 6.7 g. of a colorless product which on repeated crystallisation from ligroin melted at 125-26°. There was no depression in melting point on admixture with a synthetic sample of 2-hydroxy-2'-methyldiphenylsulphone (*vide infra*). (Found: C, 62.4; H, 4.9. Calc. for C₁₃H₁₂O₂S: C, 62.9; H, 4.8%). The ligroin-insoluble portion was chiefly the isomeric *p*-hydroxysulphone. It remained as a semi-solid and could not be crystallised from any of the common solvents.

2-Methoxy-2'-methyldiphenyl Sulphide.—To a solution of sodium ethoxide (1.9 g. of sodium in 25 c.c. of absolute ethanol) *o*-thiocresol (10 g.) was added and evaporated to dryness. This was treated with *o*-iodoanisole (20.8 g.) and copper powder (1 g.) and heated at 230-40° for 3 hours. The product, after cooling, was mixed with zinc dust (10 g.) and sulphuric acid (1:1; 50 c.c.) and steam-distilled. The residue was extracted with ether, evaporation of which gave 17.4 g. (87%) of the sulphide. It boiled at 171°/12.5 mm and melted at 55-56°. (Found: C, 72.8; H, 6.3. C₁₄H₁₄OS requires C, 73.1; H, 6.1%).

2-Methoxy-2'-methyldiphenylsulphone.—A solution of the foregoing sulphide (4.6 g.) in glacial acetic acid was treated with excess of a 5% KMnO₄ solution and kept aside for 30 minutes. It was decolorised with SO₂, diluted with water and cooled. The sulphone separating was filtered off and washed with water, yield 4.8 g. (92%). On crystallising from ethanol it melted at 140-42°. (Found: C, 64.3; H, 5.3. C₁₄H₁₄O₂S requires C, 64.1; H, 5.3%).

2-Hydroxy-2'-methyldiphenylsulphone.—A mixture of the above sulphone (2.62 g.) and HI (*d* 1.7, 8 c.c.) was heated at 190-200° for 4 hours. On cooling, a reddish brown viscous mass, which solidified gradually, was obtained. It was dissolved in a 10% solution of NaOH, filtered and the filtrate acidified. The hydroxysulphone was obtained in quantitative yield (2.4 g.). After crystallising from ethanol it melted at 125-26°. (Found: C, 62.9; H, 5.1. C₁₃H₁₂O₂S requires C, 62.9; H, 4.8%).

4-Methoxy-2'-methyldiphenyl sulphide was prepared from 4-iodoanisole (20.8 g.) and *o*-thiocresol (10 g.). The experimental procedure was the same as that used for the 2-methoxy isomer. The yield was 17 g. (92%), b.p. 150-52°/12 mm. (Found: C, 72.9; H, 5.9. C₁₄H₁₄OS requires C, 73.1; H, 6.1%).

4-Methoxy-2'-methyldiphenylsulphone.—Oxidation of the foregoing sulphide with KMnO₄ solution afforded the sulphone in almost quantitative yield. It was necessary to warm the solution with KMnO₄ for a few minutes. The sulphone separated as an oil which solidified very slowly. After crystallising from ethanol it melted at 83-84°. (Found: C, 63.9; H, 5.6. C₁₄H₁₄O₂S requires C, 64.1; H, 5.3%).

The above sulphone was heated with hydriodic acid at 180° for 3 hours. The product so obtained was completely soluble in alkali. It remained as a semi-solid for more than a month. It could not be crystallised.

p-Chlorophenyl *o*-toluenesulphonate was prepared from *p*-chlorophenol and *o*-toluenesulphonyl chloride in the usual way. Crystallisation from ethanol gave needles, m.p. 63-65°. (Found: C, 55.2; H, 3.7. $C_{13}H_{11}O_2ClS$ requires C, 55.2; H, 3.9%).

The Fries Rearrangement of p-Chlorophenyl *o*-Toluenesulphonate.—The sulphate (5.6 g.) was heated with anhydrous aluminium chloride (8 g.) at 110-20° for 45 minutes. The product, when worked up as usual, gave the hydroxysulphone (0.8 g., 14%). On crystallisation from ethanol it melted at 111-12° with or without a synthetic sample of 5-chloro-2-hydroxy-2'-methyldiphenylsulphone. (Found: C, 51.7; H, 4.3. Calc. for $C_{13}H_{11}O_2ClS, H_2O$: C, 51.9; H, 4.3%).

5-Chloro-2-methoxy-2'-methyldiphenyl sulphide was prepared from *o*-iodotoluene (21.8 g.) and 5-chloro-2-methoxythiophenol (Gauntlette and Smiles, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 2745) (17.4 g.) by heating in the presence of copper; yield 21.3 g. (81%), b.p. 178-80°/8 mm. (Found: C, 63.1; H, 5.0. $C_{14}H_{13}OCIS$ requires C, 63.5; H, 4.9%).

5-Chloro-2-methoxy-2'-methyldiphenylsulphone.—Oxidation of the foregoing sulphide in acetic acid with $KMnO_4$ solution gave this compound (85%). After crystallising from ethanol it melted at 139-40°. (Found: C, 56.9; H, 4.7. $C_{14}H_{13}O_2ClS$ requires C, 56.7; H, 4.4%).

5-Chloro-2-hydroxy-2'-methyldiphenylsulphone was obtained by demethylating the above sulphone with HI in 92% yield. On crystallisation from ethanol it melted at 111-12°. (Found: C, 51.7; H, 4.0. $C_{13}H_{11}O_2ClS, H_2O$ requires C, 51.9; H, 4.3%).

The Fries Rearrangement of p-Tolyl *o*-Toluenesulphonate.—By heating the sulphate (5.24 g.) with aluminium chloride (4 g.) at 130-40° for 45 minutes and working up the product as usual, 1.94 g. (37%) of the hydroxysulphone was obtained. After crystallising from ethanol it melted at 153-54° with or without a synthetic sample of 2-hydroxy-5:2'-dimethyldiphenylsulphone. (Found: C, 63.7; H, 5.2. Calc. for $C_{14}H_{14}O_2S$: C, 64.1; H, 5.3%).

2-Methoxy-5:2'-dimethyldiphenyl sulphide was obtained from 2-methoxy-5-methylthiophenol (15.4 g.) and *o*-iodotoluene (21.8 g.) in 86% yield. It melted at 64-65° after crystallising from acetic acid. (Found: C, 73.8; H, 6.4. $C_{15}H_{14}OS$ requires C, 73.8; H, 6.6%).

2-Methoxy-5:2'-dimethyldiphenylsulphone.—Oxidation of the foregoing sulphide afforded this compound in 85% yield. On crystallisation from acetic acid it melted at 133-35°. (Found: C, 65.6; H, 6.2. $C_{15}H_{14}O_2S$ requires C, 65.2; H, 5.8%).

2-Hydroxy-5:2'-dimethyldiphenylsulphone.—Demethylation of the foregoing sulphone yielded this compound in almost quantitative yield. On crystallising from ethanol it melted at 153-54°. (Found: C, 63.8; H, 5.0. $C_{14}H_{14}O_2S$ requires C, 64.1; H, 5.3%).

p-Tolyl Ethanesulphonate.—Ethanesulphonyl chloride was added slowly to *p*-cresol in a 5% solution of NaOH and shaken well for a few minutes. The sulphonate was obtained in 86% yield; b.p. 153-54°/13.5 mm. (Found: C, 54.4; H, 5.9. $C_9H_{12}O_2S$ requires C, 54.0; H, 6.0%).

p-Tolyl Phenylmethanesulphonate.—Esterification of *p*-cresol with phenylmethanesulphonylchloride (Johnson and Sprague, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 58, 1348) furnished this compound. After recrystallising from ethanol it melted at 76-78°. (Found: C, 63.9; H, 5.5. $C_{14}H_{14}O_2S$ requires C, 64.1; H, 5.3%).

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